

Synthesis and characterization of hexanuclear diazenido oxotungstate cluster (NBu₄)₄ [(W₆O₁₇)(NNC₆H₅)₂]

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(NBu₄)₄[(W₆O₁₇)(NNC₆H₅)₂] has been synthesised as bluish white crystalline material. The cluster has been characterized by IR and UV-Vis spectra. Preliminary X-ray diffraction studies confirmed the crystal to be orthorhombic having space group *Pmcn* with *a* = 17.85 Å; *b* = 18.65 Å; *c* = 21.67 Å; *V* = 7213.58 Å³; *Z* = 4; *D_c* = 2.35 g cm⁻³.

The coordination chemistry of polytungstates with small organic molecule in their entity is of much interest in the development of models for the interaction of organic substrate with catalytic oxide surfaces^{1,2}. Since the solvent has great influence in the aggregation process of various isopoly oxometallates, hence it is expected that the variation of the solvent in reaction process, may yield novel composition for organo-diazenido-derivatized polyoxotungstate³. In the present communication we report synthesis and characterization of hexanuclear diazenido-oxotungstate cluster, (NBu₄)₄[(W₆O₁₇)(NNC₆H₅)₂].

Results and discussion

The synthesized cluster is stable in air (Found : W, 43.54; N, 4.54; C, 35.52; H, 5.92. (NBu₄)₄[(W₆O₁₇)(NNC₆H₅)₂] requires : W, 43.20; N, 4.39; C, 35.72; H, 6.04%). The IR spectra of the compound confirmed the presence of the characteristic terminal and bridge oxo groups as ascertained by $\nu(\text{W}-\text{O}_t) = 975 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu(\text{W}-\text{O}_b) = 810 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ⁴ and $\nu(\text{W}-\text{O}_c) = 760 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The sharp peak at 1595 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, confirmed the presence of coordinated phenylhydrazenido unit in the complex. $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ indicated an upward shift⁵ of IR absorption by about 20 cm^{-1} , supporting the involvement of one of the nitrogen of N-N group coordinatively bound with tungsten (W-NNR). The UV-visible spectra showed three bands in UV region at 245, 280 and 320 nm and in the visible region at 410 and 470 nm, the later⁶ may be associated with W[NNC₆H₅] chromophore.

Preliminary X-ray data of the crystalline sample were recorded. The density was determined by floatation method using carbon tetrachloride bromoform mixture. The crystal data, collected in CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5412 \text{ \AA}$) with Ni filter, are as follows for (NBu₄)₄[(W₆O₁₇)(NNC₆H₅)₂] : *M* = 2553, orthorhombic space group *Pmcn*, *a* = 17.85 Å; *b* =

18.65 Å; *c* = 21.67 Å; volume per unit cell, *V* = 7213.58 Å³, no. of unit cell contained, *Z* = 4; *D_c* = 2.35 g cm⁻³. 750 reflection out of 2500 collected, were used for the present investigation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. The solvent was freshly distilled before use. Reaction of a suspension of [(NBu₄)₂(W₆O₁₉)] (2.371 g = 1.253 mmol) in dry benzene with an equivalent amount of phenyl hydrazine (0.197 g = 1.824 mmol), resulted a bluish white coloured solution after 5 h reflux. The reaction mixture was slowly evaporated and left overnight for crystallization, when bluish-white orthorhombic crystals separated. The product was washed with pet-ether and dried in vacuum.

For complete analysis of the compound, tungsten was estimated using A.R.L. 3410 (Switzerland) atomic emission spectrophotometer and C H N by Coleman analyser. IR spectra (KBr) of the compound was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ and the X-ray data on a D 500/501 (Siemens) instrument.

Three dimensional X-ray crystal structure of the compound with appreciable degree of refinement, may confirm the presence of discrete hexanuclear unit of [W₆O₁₉]²⁻, incorporating two coordinatively bound phenylhydrazenido groups, replacing two terminal oxo units of hexatungstate moiety giving rise to the metal cluster (NBu₄)₄[(W₆O₁₇)(NNC₆H₅)₂]. The details will be presented in our subsequent publication.

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